

1 **HTR1D and HTR3A mobilization during lineage specification in embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 HTR1D and HTR3A as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the human
10 embryo.

11 Citations

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1. Romero-Reyes, J., Molina-Hernández, A., Díaz, N.F. and Camacho-Arroyo, I., 2021. Role of
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